

THE ITALIAN FACILITY FOR LUNAR MISSIONS SIMULATION AND OPERATION

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The current main effort of Exploration is focused on the return to the Moon surface, in preparation of a future phase of foundational and then sustained presence over the long term, as also reflected in the Global Exploration Roadmap 2024 elaborated by the International Space Exploration Coordination Group (ISECG) [1]. In this frame, ASI is a major player leading several initiatives aimed at contributing to fostering space research and developing key technologies; among them, it is worth to mention the ISRU technological demonstrator ORACLE [2] and the lunar Multipurpose Habitation Module.

This global scenario induced ASI to establish a ground infrastructure in support of the preparation and implementation of lunar missions, mainly for national initiatives but also potentially open to the international space community. ALTEC, an Italian company with strong heritage in mission preparation and control, acquired through support to International Space Station utilization as well as the ESA ExoMars program, has been selected to develop and to host the facility, in Turin. The activities started in December 2023 and are planned to end after 36 months.

The lunar facility will include a Lunar Terrain Simulator, a large area in the size of about 25 x 16.8 m² that can be used as indoor analogue of the lunar surface, to test different exploration scenarios. The terrain will be obtained by a thick layer of simulant replicating lunar regolith properties particularly relevant for the execution of the use cases tests. On one side of the arena, an 8x8 m² tiltable platform will be positioned to simulate slopes up to 25 degrees, while another area could be outfitted, if needed, to simulate natural caves like the lunar pit of a lava tube entrance. The whole area will be equipped with a complex light system, to mimic the sunlight conditions at different latitudes of the Moon. A complex crane will allow to perform logistic operations and also to install a lifting device with the function of gravity compensation on the items under test, both robotic systems and crew.

One additional optional element for the infrastructure, at the moment under evaluation, will be a dirty thermo-vacuum chamber to replicate the environmental lunar conditions, including the presence of regolith bench in various grain size distributions.

The third element of the infrastructure will be a Lunar Mission Control Centre, with functions and connectivity set to monitor the testing activities and to operate robotic and crewed missions in cislunar and surface environment for real lunar missions [3].

As relevant part of the design phase of LTS, comparative detailed study has been dedicated to the selection of the lunar regolith simulant. The drivers for this analysis came from the established use cases and from the type of testing that are planned to be executed in the different environments of the facility. A survey of existing or under-preparation analogue terrain facilities was also completed as market analysis, as well as the state-of-the-art documentation [4]

The different simulants already adopted in similar sites were compared, in terms of parameters of representativeness, with particular focus on geotechnical features. Impacts due to safety and in respect of the operators' health were carefully considered and mitigation countermeasures envisioned. The procurement constraints, impacted by the large amount of necessary material, were also accounted, in particular considering national possible suppliers.

This preparatory work allowed the selection of the best lunar simulant material, to be procured for the LTS facility as terrain for surface operations of robotic elements and crew.

Figure 1 – Artistic view of the Lunar Terrain Simulator

References:

- [1] Global Exploration Roadmap 2024, [Online]. <https://www.globalspaceexploration.org/wp-content/isecg/GER2024.pdf>
- [2] Prinetto, J. et al., Terrestrial demonstrator for a low-temperature carbothermal reduction process on lunar regolith simulant: design and AIV activities, *Planet. Space Sci.* 225 (2023)
- [3] “NASA Lunar Regolith Simulant User’s guide – Revision A” – NASA/TM-20240011783, October 2024.
- [4] R. Messineo et. al., “Multi-mission MSC & SDC: shared infrastructures, frameworks and facilities for ground segment”. IAC 2024 Conference, 14-18 October, Milan, 2024.